

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Service needs of elderly members in Bangkok Youth Center (Thai-Japan)

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Abstract

The objective of this research is to study the service needs and factors related to elderly members who use the services of the Bangkok Youth Center (Thai-Japan). The study used a questionnaire survey as a data collection tool for 200 samples. The statistics used in the data analysis were frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, t-test (Independent Sample t-test, F-test (Independent Sample F-test) One-way ANOVA, and the Pearson's correlation coefficient to test the relationship between variables. According to the study, the majority of the samples were men, between 60 – 65 years old, marital status, had a bachelor's degree, owned business as a career before retirement, did not work after retirement and had a monthly income of 20,001-50,000 baht. The results of testing the demographic factors on service needs, by using t-test and F-test statistics, showed that the different of gender, age, status, career before retirement and career after retirement were not different, whereas educational and monthly income were. The result of testing the motivation factors on service needs, by using the Pearson's correlation coefficient statistic, showed that both intrinsic motives and extrinsic motives were related in medium level in the same way. Therefore, the study's results could be useful for involved organization for operation planning.

Keyword :Needs; Elderly; Service quality; Motivation

1. Introduction

Currently, the world has entered the era of an increasing aging population. The United Nations has estimated that from 2001 to 2100, there will be more than 10% of the global population aged 60 and above. The UN defines the elderly as males and females aged 60 years and above and categorizes the entry into an aging society into three levels: 1. Aging Society, 2. Aged Society, and 3. Super-aged Society (Aging Society: Sukhothai Thamathirat University, 2014).

Thailand has been an aging society since 2005 and continues to be. Today, there are over 12 million people, or about one-sixth of the Thai population, who are aged 60 and above (Kasemsup, V. 2022). Preparing public health and social care for the elderly, especially those who are not physically healthy and confined to their homes or beds, is crucial. As of December 31, 2023, Thailand's population was 65,061,190, with 13,064,929 elderly, constituting 20.08%, indicating that Thailand has fully entered an aged society. This situation requires significant attention and preparation.

The elderly population is incredibly valuable to society, serving as transmitters of knowledge and wisdom. They are advisors for the younger generation and should be provided with good well-being, including physical, mental, social, and intellectual well-being (Intaprasert, P. 2021).

The Bangkok Youth Center (Thai-Japan) operates under the Department of Culture, Sports, and Tourism. It offers over 45 different sports, recreational activities, and projects daily for all ages, including multiple activities for the elderly, averaging 90 senior participants per day. Additionally, Bangkok's Governor, Chadchart Sittipunt, has set health-related policies, including the Elderly Club for Active Aging, supporting knowledge activities and paperwork for club setup, and

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facilitating spaces for group activities and club rooms designed to be convenient and pleasant for seniors. These policies aim to ensure mental and physical health for the elderly, contributing to the community as a reservoir of wisdom. Given these policies, the study aims to understand the needs of elderly members using the services at the Bangkok Youth Center (Thai-Japan) to plan service management effectively. The study objectives are 1. To investigate the needs of elderly members who use the services of the Bangkok Youth Center (Thai-Japan). 2. To explore the factors associated with the needs of elderly members at the Bangkok Youth Center (Thai-Japan).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Concepts on the Elderly

The Department of Senior Affairs defines elderly individuals as those aged 60 and above, entitled to protection, promotion, and support in over 16 areas including:

- Sports and Recreation: Elderly should access health checks, services in health parks, sports fields, gyms, aerobics areas, and petanque courts, and participate in activities such as sports competitions, dancing, and physical fitness tests.
- Self-development: Elderly should be encouraged and supported to engage in social activities within and between communities, contributing to social networks of the elderly, and fostering their potential through sports, recreation, and knowledge transfer.

2.2. Concepts on Needs

Needs refer to desires that cause changes within an individual, driven by internal forces and external stimuli. These desires are relentless and cyclic, continuously evolving after they are satisfied. Human needs fall into two categories:

1. Physiological Needs: These are primary drives associated with survival and physical well-being, occurring naturally without learning, spurred by body demands.

2. Psychological and Social Needs: These are complex and arise from social conditions, culture, learning, and experiences, varying across individuals and social contexts.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs outlines five levels of human needs 1) Physiological Needs: Basic body requirements. 2) Safety Needs: Security and safety. 3) Belonging and Love Needs: Emotional relationships and social acceptance. 4) Esteem Needs: Recognition and self-esteem. 5) Self-actualization Needs: Achieving one's potential.

In summary, needs are ongoing desires that drive individuals to fulfill them, leading to satisfaction and new desires, affecting both physical and mental states.

2.3. Concepts on Motivation

Motivation refers to the factors that influence or prompt actions or behaviors. It is a process where individuals are stimulated by various triggers, striving to achieve a particular goal. Treesuwan, S. (2005) defines work motivation as the internal and external drives that stimulate the direction or approach of behavior, allowing an individual to perform various tasks willingly and according to their personal motivation. Motivation can be categorized into two types:

1. Intrinsic Motives: These are driven by internal psychological desires, influencing our behavior, thoughts, attitudes, interests, preferences, or beliefs, and are expressed through our actions. This type of motivation is generally enduring and results in consistent and long-term behavioral expressions.

2. Extrinsic Motives: These are motivations stimulated by external factors, such as the desire for acceptance from others, fame, or the lure of a reward. This type drives us to act in ways that achieve and fulfill our set goals.

3. Research Methodology

This study is quantitative, utilizing a survey method with a questionnaire divided into four parts: general information of respondents, their motivations for using the center, the needs of elderly members, and suggestions. The sample consisted of 200 elderly members from the Bangkok Youth Center (Thai-Japan). The sample size was calculated using G*Power with a medium effect size of 0.25, a type I error rate of 0.05, a power of 0.90, and two groups, resulting in 172

participants. To account for potential non-response, an additional 28 were added, totaling 200 participants. Descriptive statistics used include frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. Inferential statistics include t-tests and F-tests with hypotheses focusing on demographic factors affecting service needs and the relationship of motivational factors to service needs. Pearson's correlation was used to test relationships between variables.

4. Results

4.1. General information of respondents

From a sample size of 200, it was found that the majority are males, totaling 102 individuals or 51.0%, and females are 98, making up 49.0%. The age group most represented is those aged 60 to 65 years, with 84 individuals or 42.0%, followed by those aged 65 to 70 years with 81 individuals or 40.5%, and those over 70 years old numbering 35 or 17.5%. Regarding marital status, 89 individuals are married (44.5%), 86 are single (43.0%), and 25 are divorced (12.5%). The most common education level is a bachelor's degree with 122 individuals (61.0%), followed by high school with 33 (16.5%), postgraduate degrees with 29 (14.5%), and primary education with 16 (8.0%). The predominant pre-retirement occupation is private business ownership with 63 individuals (31.5%), followed by government/public enterprise employees at 60 (30.0%), private company employees at 42 (21.0%), and general laborers at 30 (15.0%). For post-retirement occupation, the largest group is not working, with 103 individuals (51.5%), followed by private business owners (28.5%), general laborers (12.0%), and government employees (1.5%). Most have a current monthly income ranging from 20,001 to 50,000 baht, representing 40.0% of the sample.

4.2. The needs of elderly members who use the services

From Table 1, it shows the overall level of needs of the elderly members has an average of 4.04, which is considered "high." Detailed consideration reveals that the highest needs include "lighted pathways, senior-specific bathrooms, first aid kits at all points, emergency SOS call points, and a medical room."

Table 1 The means, standard deviations (S.D.), and levels of service needs among elderly members concerning facility services

Elderly Members' Service Needs	\bar{x}	S.D.	Level
Facility			
1. Ramps and handrails along walkways	4.20	0.90	high
2. Pathway/runway lighting	4.37	0.80	highest
3. Bathrooms for elderly	4.29	0.98	highest
4. Parking spots or drop-off points for elderly	4.13	0.95	high
5. Convenient and clean drinking water stations	4.15	1.06	high
6. Medical room	4.23	0.99	highest
7. Park benches around the center	4.09	0.88	high
8. Elevators for elderly	3.84	1.16	high
9. Health food stores	3.68	1.18	high
10. Reading nooks under trees	3.68	1.21	high
Tools and Equipment			
11. Free and comprehensive WiFi signal	3.65	1.23	high
12. First Aid kits at all locations	4.28	0.99	highest
13. Emergency help points (SOS CALL POINT)	4.24	1.01	highest
14. Pneumatic exercise equipment	3.79	0.82	high
Staff			
15. Medical personnel	4.20	0.90	high
16. Uniformed staff	3.48	1.08	high
Activity Services			
17. Exercise plans for specific diseases	4.09	0.86	high

18. Health screenings before services	4.18	0.84	high
19. Elderly Day activities at the center	4.19	0.85	high
20. Massage therapy for injuries	4.08	0.93	high
Overall	4.04	0.98	high

4.3. The factors associated with the needs of elderly members

From Table 2, the demographic test results can be categorized as follows:

- Gender: No significant statistical difference at the 0.05 level in service needs among members based on gender.
- Age: No significant statistical difference at the 0.05 level in service needs among elderly members based on age.
- Marital Status: No significant statistical difference at the 0.05 level in service needs among elderly members based on marital status.
- Education Level: There is a significant statistical difference at the 0.05 level in service needs among elderly members based on education level.
- Occupation Before Retirement: No significant statistical difference at the 0.05 level in service needs among elderly members based on occupation before retirement.
- Occupation After Retirement: No significant statistical difference at the 0.05 level in service needs among elderly members based on occupation after retirement.
- Current Monthly Income: There is a significant statistical difference at the 0.05 level in service needs among elderly members based on current monthly income.

Table 2 The number and average of the sample group categorized by demographic factors, analyzing the differences in these demographic factors concerning the service needs of elderly members.

Demographic Factors	N	\bar{x}	S.D.	t	F	Sig.
Gender						
Male	102	4.09	0.70	1.880		0.620
Female	98	3.91	0.69			
Age						
From 60 to under 65 years	84	3.92	0.78	1.238		0.292
From 65 to under 70 years	81	4.09	0.65			
70 years and above	35	4.03	0.57			
Marital Status					0.205	0.815
Single	86	4.01	0.67			
Married	89	4.03	0.74			
Divorced	25	3.93	0.62			
Education Level						
Primary Education	16	3.89	0.73	3.400		0.019**
Secondary Education	33	3.70	0.80			
Bachelor’s Degree	122	4.07	0.67			
Master’s/Doctoral Degree	29	4.17	0.59			
Occupation Before Retirement					1.042	0.387
Own Business	63	4.08	0.55			
Government Employee	60	4.09	0.59			
Private Company Employee	42	3.96	0.82			
General Worker	30	3.84	0.87			
Other	5	3.71	1.15			

Occupation After Retirement					2.083	0.068
Own Business	57	3.98	0.71			
Government Contract Worker	3	4.27	0.59			
General Worker	24	4.33	0.58			
Private Company Employee	10	3.65	0.99			
Unemployed	103	3.99	0.66			
Other	3	3.49	0.93			
Current Income, Average per Month					4.625	0.004**
Up to 15,000 THB	46	3.80	0.84			
15,001-20,000 THB	52	4.11	0.64			
20,001-50,000 THB	80	3.95	0.66			
Over 50,000 THB	22	4.41	0.34			

Sig < 0.05**

From Table 3, the research findings indicate that both internal and external motivational factors significantly correlate with the service needs of elderly members at a statistical significance level of 0.01.

Table 3 Analyzes the relationship between motivational factors and service needs of elderly members.

Motivational Factors	Pearson's correlation coefficient (r)	
	Elderly Members' Service Needs	Interpretation
1. Intrinsic Motivation		
Desire to exercise	0.335**	Low correlation
Desire for good, age-appropriate physique	0.250**	Low correlation
Desire for recreational activities	0.470**	Moderate correlation
Desire to meet peers	0.469**	Moderate correlation
Desire to be a senior athlete	0.317**	Low correlation
2. Extrinsic Motivation		
Convenience of location for access	0.379**	Low correlation
Availability of facilities	0.495**	Moderate correlation
Sufficient space for various activities	0.444**	Moderate correlation
Diverse and interesting activities	0.462**	Moderate correlation
Regular attendance by peers	0.489**	Moderate correlation

Sig < 0.01**

5. Discussion

The study concludes that demographic factors such as gender, age, marital status, and occupations before and after retirement, which vary among individuals, show no significant difference in service needs among elderly members. This is consistent with the study by Damrongsiri, T. (2023), suggesting that demographic characteristics like gender, age, and profession do not influence the decision-making regarding the selection of nursing care services within the Bangkok Metropolitan Area. This aligns with the findings of Police Lieutenant Phongphichit Jindawanit (2020), who observed that personal factors such as gender, age, and profession do not vary in terms of recreational needs among the users of Chatuchak Park. However, educational levels and current monthly incomes that differ do affect the service needs among the elderly, contrary to Damrongsiri, T. (2023) and Siriphanpanya, J. (2022), who noted that educational levels and

annual incomes do not influence satisfaction with the government welfare card scheme. The discrepancy might be due to elderly members with higher education levels and incomes having access to better quality service options to meet their needs.

The study on internal motivation shows a significant positive correlation at a moderate level ($p=0.01$) between high internal motivation and increased service needs of the elderly. Internal motivation, associated with personal psychological factors, can enhance the desire for activities like exercise, reducing stress and improving social and self-confidence. This aligns with Chatchawanwit, A. (2003) who highlighted the psychological impact of internal motivation on the desire to exercise and social adjustments. External motivation was also found to have a significant positive correlation at a moderate level ($p=0.01$) with service needs of the elderly, suggesting that when external motivational factors increase, they complement and enhance internal motivational drives, leading to a higher likelihood of achieving set goals. This complements findings by Brainfit (2022) and Supprasert, T., and Saensuk, J. (2021), noting that external factors like adequate facilities and social support impact the behavioral tendencies towards physical activities.

Recommendations

- The study found that demographic factors such as gender, age, marital status, and pre- and post-retirement occupations did not significantly influence service needs, whereas educational level and current monthly income did. Therefore, the Bangkok Youth Center (Thai-Japan) can develop policies or strategies that are appropriate and encompass the needs of all elderly people.
- Motivational factors were found to correlate with service needs, with external motivation being the strongest. The Bangkok Youth Center (Thai-Japan) can use this data to plan and design services that further motivate elderly people to use their services.
- Both internal and external motivations, particularly social interactions and meeting peers, were highly motivating. Agencies could use this information to plan spaces or activities that increase social opportunities for the elderly, helping reduce isolation and depression.
- Facility-related needs such as lighting on walkways, elderly-specific bathrooms, and medical rooms were of highest demand, reflecting a significant concern for safety among the elderly. Relevant organizations should consider enhancing or remodeling these facilities to cater not only to the elderly but also to disabled individuals.

6. Conclusion

The study of the needs of elderly members at the Bangkok Youth Center (Thai-Japan) reveals multifaceted needs concerning service locations, tools, personnel, and activity offerings. This information will be invaluable for the Youth Center in developing policies and strategies that appropriately cater to and encompass the needs of all elderly individuals, creating spaces and activities that encourage more social interaction, outdoor time, and help reduce depression. Design considerations should focus on convenience and safety, ensuring facilities are also accessible to disabled persons.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

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